

Feature-Based Modelling of Perceived Emotion in Film Music

Ruby Olivia Nagano Crocker¹ and Gyorgy Fazekas¹

Queen Mary University of London, Mile End Road, London E1 4NS
{r.o.n.crocker, g.fazekas}@qmul.ac.uk
<https://www.aim.qmul.ac.uk/>

Abstract. This study investigates how musical features in film scores relate to perceived emotional expression over time. Film music differs from general music, as it is designed to manipulate narrative, tension, and audience perception, providing context-specific emotional cues beyond melody or harmony. The study is based on the FME-24 dataset, a collection of 300 professionally composed film score excerpts (2002–2024) covering both contemporary and traditional practices, through which perceptual, rhythmic, and tonal features were analysed. Participants marked moments of perceived emotional change, described the emotion, and placed it in a valence–arousal space. The preliminary results showed that emotions were clearly perceived but often difficult to verbalize. Analysis showed weak but significant correlations for certain features (e.g. ZCR and arousal), while chord types influenced arousal more strongly. Rhythmic and tonal features showed varied relationships with both dimensions. Arousal was generally perceived more consistently than valence. Isolating audio enables more precise mapping between musical features and perceived emotion, establishing a baseline for future audiovisual comparisons. Variability in participant reports highlights the subjectivity of film music perception and supports further feature-based modelling of emotional dynamics in cinematic scoring.

Keywords: Music Emotion Recognition · Music Information Retrieval · Film Composition

1 Introduction

Music plays a vital role in film, shaping narrative and enhancing emotional impact. Understanding how film scores evoke emotion requires examining the relationship between musical features and listener perception over time. This study focuses on perceived emotion, capturing how listeners interpret musical expression through time-stamped annotations of emotional change. We analyze these responses using the FME-24 dataset, a curated collection of 300 film score excerpts spanning 2002–2024 [6]. In music emotion recognition (MER), emotions are studied as either induced; listeners' internal affective states measured via physiological or behavioral responses, or perceived, the emotions listeners attribute to the music. This study focuses on perceived emotion, providing rich,

temporally aligned data for dimensional and semantic analysis. Although film music is usually paired with visuals, this study isolates audio to examine its standalone emotional impact. Research shows that music alone can evoke stronger emotions than video-only or combined contexts [28]. Removing visuals highlights musical structure, harmony, and rhythm, the core drivers of emotional narrative. It allows for investigation of how film scores remain emotionally powerful without cinematic context, although it may increase interpretive variability. Combining music theory, psychology, and music information retrieval (MIR), this research uses timestamped annotations, feature extraction, and semantic clustering to study how composers shape emotional trajectories. Since emotion in narrative film composition is underexplored in MIR, this study fills that gap, offering data-driven insights relevant to both research and creative practice.

2 Related Work

Film music is a powerful tool for conveying emotion, with research focusing on its impact on audience emotion perceptions. Unlike standalone music datasets, which emphasize listening in isolation, film music is composed to serve narrative, manipulating emotion, guiding perception, and providing context-specific cues beyond text or visuals [27]. To capture this function, the FME-24 dataset was developed and used in this study [6].

Recent work highlights a shift from classical traditions toward experimental and electronic approaches, particularly in genres like horror, where “non-musical” and atmospheric elements challenge conventions [1]. This has led researchers to critique genre-based classifications as overly restrictive, since modern scores often blend styles and transcend traditional categories [12]. Enabled by digital tools, contemporary award-winning films increasingly feature hybrid and electronic scoring, yet studies show these diverse practices evoke emotions as effectively as classical forms [20], underscoring that emotional impact is not limited to traditional structures. However, despite these stylistic developments, systematic modelling of how film music evokes emotion remains underexplored.

2.1 Emotion Models

Emotion research uses discrete models that categorize basic emotions (e.g., fear, happiness) and dimensional models that represent emotions along continuous axes such as arousal and valence [26]. Music emotion studies mainly adopt these frameworks, with arousal-valence favored for its empirical support and clarity.

Musical emotions often differ from everyday emotions in quality and expression, especially in film music, which evokes narrative-driven feelings like tension, anticipation, and hope, terms less common in typical music vocabularies [24]. The FME-24 dataset reflects this distinct semantic profile, highlighting the need for models that capture film score emotions more precisely.

The Geneva Emotional Music Scale (GEMS) offers nine music-specific emotion categories for a nuanced perspective beyond valence and arousal [2], but

lacks integration with dimensional models, limiting its ability to track continuous emotional changes.

This study centers on perceived emotions within the arousal-valence framework, enhanced by qualitative descriptions and semantic clustering to better capture film music’s emotional complexity.

2.2 Features

Significant research in music emotion recognition (MER) focuses on identifying audio features linked to emotion, especially within the valence-arousal model. However, existing models often miss aspects of musical expressivity and texture [21].

MER features fall into two main types: audio-based (low-level acoustic properties like timbre, pitch, rhythm, intensity) and symbolic (higher-level structural elements like chord progressions and key clarity) [29]. Combining both provides a fuller representation of musical style and emotion.

Key acoustic features include MFCCs, spectral centroid, brightness, and inharmonicity, which influence qualities such as sharpness and energy [13]. Rhythmic features such as tempo and beat strength affect perceived intensity and expressiveness [9]. Perceptual features, articulation, pitch salience, danceability, and chord information, also strongly shape emotional perception [11, 22].

Tools like Librosa [19], Essentia [4], MIRToolbox [17], and Chordino [18] enable extraction of these features, with Chordino providing chord timestamps crucial for analyzing harmonic emotion [10].

This multidimensional feature approach underpins modelling of perceived emotion, especially in complex settings like film music where acoustic texture and structure shape emotional narratives.

3 Methods

This study investigates the relationship between perceived emotional changes and musical features in film music, using data collected via an online annotation task, followed by audio feature extraction and analysis. As well as a preliminary subset participant experiment and classification of the soundtrack type.

3.1 Online Data collection

Data was collected via a secure web interface where participants listened to 15-second excerpts from the FME-24 dataset. They pressed a button upon perceiving emotional changes, adjusted a color-coded dot on a valence–arousal graph, added brief text descriptions, and rated familiarity (see Figure 1) [6]. A tutorial on the valence–arousal space preceded the task, with an optional help button offering emotion adjectives from established mood models [16]. Quality-control measures ensured reliable responses, and after screening for outliers, $N = 93$ participants’ annotations were included in the analysis.

Fig. 1. Online Interactive Survey for Emotion annotation collection

3.2 Feature Extraction

Audio features were extracted around participant-annotated emotional change points using two temporal windowing strategies. Change-Based Windowing involved two 2-second windows before and after each change (e.g., 0–2s and 2–4s) to capture directional shifts in musical properties. Center-Aligned Windowing used a single 1-second window centered on the change (0.5–1.5s), suitable for perceptual and rhythmic features needing contextual symmetry. This dual approach accommodates how low-level features reflect directional changes, while higher-level perceptual features represent broader states, consistent with known perceptual buffer times for emotion recognition [3, 23].

Acoustic Features Extracted via Librosa [19] and related toolkits, these low-level spectral and temporal descriptors include MFCCs (mean and variance of 13 coefficients), spectral centroid, bandwidth, rolloff, contrast, zero-crossing rate, and chroma-STFT (12 pitch bins). They relate closely to perceptual qualities such as timbre, pitch content, and rhythm, with MFCC variance indicating emotional consistency or irregularities [5, 13].

Perceptually Motivated and Rhythmic Features: To capture musical expressivity beyond acoustics, features including BPM, beat counts, chord types and transitions, inharmonicity (dissonance/tension [23]), pitch salience, and danceability (rhythmic regularity and energy [15]) were extracted. These span multiple timescales critical for film music’s emotional narratives: chord progressions and harmonic shifts signal emotional change; inharmonicity induces unease; pitch salience highlights key moments; tempo modulates scene pacing and mood; and danceability influences physical engagement [15]. Combined with acoustic fea-

tures, these provide a comprehensive, explainable framework for modelling musical emotion in film scoring.

3.3 Data Analysis

To explore how audio feature changes relate to arousal and valence shifts, we used Spearman’s rank correlation to measure relationships and Cohen’s d to quantify change magnitude. We extracted 43 audio features using Change-Based and Center-Aligned Windowing. Non-normal data distributions (confirmed by Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests) led us to choose Spearman’s correlation and Cohen’s d for effect size around emotional transitions.

Emotion Space Segmentation The arousal-valence space was divided into four quadrants: Q1 (High Arousal, High Valence), Q2 (High Arousal, Low Valence), Q3 (Low Arousal, Low Valence), and Q4 (Low Arousal, High Valence), plus a neutral point at (0,0) for ambiguous segments. Transitions between quadrants grouped feature changes to evaluate emotional shifts, focusing on rhythmic, tonal, and perceptual features. This method combined with Change-Based Windowing to compare feature dynamics before and after transitions.

3.4 Preliminary Participant Experiment

In the preliminary subset, most participants noted emotional changes in Songs 3–8, while Songs 1 and 2 elicited more varied, ambiguous reactions. Beyond common emotions like “happy” and “relaxed,” they used imagery, movement, and texture to describe feelings. Some felt uncertain or “emotionally illiterate,” often resorting to non-emotional descriptions, highlighting annotation challenges. Responses from CBT therapists, speech therapists, and musicians showed no clear consensus.

3.5 Soundtrack Type Classification

Tracks were labeled as original (1), sourced (0), or mixed (0/1), with most annotations for original scores (1375), then sourced (253), and mixed (52). Emotional intensity was measured by each annotation’s distance from the neutral point (0,0) in arousal-valence space, categorised into neutral, moderate, or strong zones. The hypothesis is that original scores, designed to support narrative and evoke emotion, elicit stronger responses than sourced tracks, consistent with prior research [28]. Results appear in Section 4.7.

4 Results

This section presents findings on how musical features affect emotional perception. It covers participant agreement on emotion ratings, links between features and emotional changes. It includes analyses of spectral, harmonic, rhythmic, and perceptual features, chord extraction, participant insights, and annotation consistency.

4.1 Participant Emotion Agreement

Consistency in emotional annotation was evaluated using range, interquartile range (IQR), cosine similarity, and Euclidean distance metrics across participants. Arousal ratings demonstrated stronger alignment than valence, with lower variation and higher cosine similarity, indicating greater consensus on changes in arousal. These findings align with previous research [8, 14]. See Table 1 for detailed values.

	Range	IQR	Cosine Sim.	Euc. Dist.
Arousal	1.934	0.54775	0.3256	0.1958
Valence	1.941	0.66025	0.2495	0.1940

Table 1. Comparison of Range, IQR, Cosine Similarity, and Euclidean Distance for Arousal and Valence

4.2 Spectral & Temporal Features

Zero-crossing rate (ZCR) showed a weak but significant association with arousal ($r=0.05$, $p=0.03$) and a notable effect size (Cohen’s $d = -1.17$), suggesting that smoother, more harmonic segments tend to accompany heightened arousal. Other spectral features had minimal or non-significant correlations with either arousal or valence 2.

Feat.	SC_A	pSC_A	SC_V	pSC_V	Cd_A	Cd_V
ZCR	0.052	0.033	-0.016	0.501	-1.166	-0.258
S.Cont	0.028	0.258	0.017	0.475	-0.584	-0.579
S.Cent	0.026	0.294	0.013	0.589	0.041	0.041
S.Band	0.020	0.415	0.033	0.170	-0.003	-0.003
S.Roll	0.022	0.365	0.012	0.629	0.054	0.054

Table 2. Top statistically significant features from Librosa with Spearman’s Coefficient and Cohen’s d .

4.3 Harmonic Content

Chroma bins 1–2 exhibited slight positive correlations with arousal, whereas bins 3–12 tended toward negative correlations. Valence effects were minimal, suggesting harmonic shifts may subtly influence perceived energy more than mood. This highlights a potential role for pitch class emphasis in modulating emotional intensity around transitions.

4.4 Chord Types

Changes in arousal and valence were analysed for one-second segments containing a single chord, classified as augmented, diminished, major, or minor. Table 3 shows average emotional shifts, where negative values indicate decreases.

Augmented chords caused the largest decreases in both arousal (-0.31) and valence, suggesting darker, lower-energy emotions. Diminished chords slightly

Fig. 2. Spearman's Coefficient of Chroma Features for Valence and Arousal

lowered arousal but increased valence. Major chords had minimal effects, while minor chords slightly increased arousal with little change in valence, differing from previous findings linking minor chords to decreased valence [25].

ANOVA revealed a significant effect of chord type on arousal change ($p = 0.0036$) but not on valence ($p = 0.66$) (Table 4).

A weighted influence score combining mean change, variability, and frequency was used to rank chords by their emotional relevance. Rare chords like F#m7b5 scored highly, though common chords such as D major and G major also ranked prominently (Table 5). Here, $\Delta Aro \mu$ represents the mean change in arousal, and $\Delta Val \sigma$ the change in valence variability.

Type	Mean Aro Change	Mean Val Change
Augmented	-0.3055	-0.1236
Diminished	-0.1087	0.0640
Major	-0.0214	-0.0043
Minor	0.0335	-0.0001
Other	0.0547	0.0279

Table 3. Average Arousal and Valence Change by Chord Type

Chord Analysis	F-stat	p-value
Arousal Change	3.92	0.0036
Valence Change	0.60	0.6614

Table 4. ANOVA Results for Arousal and Valence Change by Chord Type

4.5 Perceptual & Rhythmic Features

High-level perceptual and rhythmic features, such as BPM, beat count, inharmonicity, pitch salience, and danceability, were analysed using the Change-Based Windowing method described in Section 3.2. This involved comparing 2-second segments immediately before and after each annotated emotional shift to assess feature evolution across emotion quadrant transitions. Key findings are summarised in the following sections, supported by tables.

Danceability Spearman correlations (Table 6) revealed a weak but significant relationship between arousal variance and danceability variance ($r = 0.074$, p

Chord	$\Delta\text{Aro } \mu$	$\Delta\text{Aro } \sigma$	$\Delta\text{Val } \mu$	$\Delta\text{Val } \sigma$	Freq	W-Score
F#m7b5	0.613	0.600	0.507	0.507	6	1.319
D	0.034	0.401	0.017	0.382	148	1.319
G	-0.033	0.389	0.067	0.466	124	1.306
C	-0.038	0.425	-0.022	0.442	131	1.291
Cm	0.085	0.319	-0.042	0.476	85	1.254
Dm	0.017	0.379	0.052	0.410	99	1.249
A	-0.105	0.449	-0.011	0.454	81	1.226
Gm	-0.034	0.430	0.001	0.450	88	1.197
Bdim	0.376	0.372	0.374	0.247	8	1.195
Em	0.066	0.372	-0.027	0.477	68	1.184

Table 5. Chord Effect on Valence and Arousal

< 0.005), indicating that emotional volatility is modestly linked with variability in danceability. No significant correlations were found with mean arousal or valence. Danceability, as a high-level feature, was analysed for its correlation with changes in valence and arousal.

Analysis of quadrant transitions (Table 7) shows that movements into high-arousal states (particularly Q1) tend to increase danceability. For instance, transitions from Q4 \rightarrow Q1 showed more increases (29) than decreases (12), suggesting that energetic emotional states may enhance the perception of danceability.

	S_C	S_Cp
Aro_Var	0.0740	0.0046
Aro_Mean	0.0127	0.6277
Val_Var	-0.0332	0.2047
Val_Mean	-0.0228	0.3824

Table 6. Spearman Correlations with p-values for Arousal, Valence, Danceability Mean and Variance

Transition	Decrease	Increase
(0,0) \rightarrow Q1	45	58
Q1 \rightarrow Q1	155	144
Q1 \rightarrow Q4	24	28
Q2 \rightarrow Q2	85	108
Q2 \rightarrow Q1	36	36
Q3 \rightarrow Q4	8	12
Q4 \rightarrow Q1	12	29

Table 7. Danceability Mean Transitions by Quadrant

BPM & Beat Count Quadrant transitions exhibited subtle but telling changes in rhythmic patterns. Beat count decreased during (0,0) \rightarrow Q1 transitions (Table 8), suggesting that emotionally intense, positive states may simplify rhythm, while Q1 \rightarrow Q4 transitions (positive \rightarrow negative) showed more decreases than increases. BPM followed a similar trend: transitions into high-arousal quadrants like Q1 generally led to stabilization or reduction, whereas Q3 (low arousal/negative valence) transitions showed greater BPM variability, reflecting emotional instability (Table 9).

Inharmonicity Table 10 indicates increased inharmonicity during transitions with negative valence (e.g., Q4 \rightarrow Q2), although statistical significance was lacking. **Pitch Saliency** Small sample sizes or high variability in arousal conditions (Q1 and Q2), inharmonicity (Table 11). For example, Q1ally, Q1 transitions showed more increases (160) than decreases (139). Interestingly, shifts toward more positive valence, even with decreasing arousal (e.g., Q1 \rightarrow Q4), also led to increases in pitch saliency, underscoring its role in marking uplifting emotional changes.

Transition	Decr	Incr	N/c
(0,0) → Q1	52	20	38
(0,0) → Q2	27	12	20
(0,0) → Q4	20	11	8
Q3 → Q2	6	15	8
Q1 → Q1	124	107	68
Q2 → Q2	72	70	51
Q3 → Q3	18	32	18
Q1 → Q4	21	16	15

Table 8. Quadrant Transitions for Beat Counts

Transition	Decr	Incr	N/c
Q4 → Q1	23	9	9
Q2 → Q3	25	7	5
Q2 → Q2	108	41	44
Q1 → Q1	172	72	55
Q2 → Q1	38	13	21
(0,0) → Q1	60	17	33

Table 9. Quadrant Transitions for BPM

Transition	Decr	Incr
Q1 → Q2	27	18
Q2 → Q1	32	17
Q3 → Q2	12	7
Q3 → Q4	5	12
Q4 → Q2	5	11

Table 10. Quadrant Transitions for Inharmonicity

Transition	Decrease	Increase
Q1 → Q1	139	160
Q2 → Q2	82	111
Q1 → Q4	20	32
Q3 → Q4	9	11

Table 11. Significant Pitch Saliency Changes Across Quadrant Transitions

4.6 Preliminary Experiment Results

Most participants noted emotional changes in Songs 3–8, while Songs 1 and 2 drew varied, ambiguous responses. Beyond common emotion words like “happy” and “relaxed,” participants used imagery (e.g., “sunrise”), movement (e.g., “gliding”), and texture (e.g., “bright”) to express feelings. Some felt “emotionally illiterate” or uncertain, often relying on visual or non-emotional descriptions, highlighting annotation challenges. Responses from diverse professionals (CBT therapists, speech therapists, musicians) showed no clear consensus.

4.7 Score vs. Soundtrack Results

To compare emotional responses to original film scores versus sourced commercial soundtracks, annotations were categorized into neutral, moderate, or strong emotional zones based on Euclidean distance from the emotional midpoint (0,0) in arousal–valence space: below 0.2 (neutral), 0.2–0.5 (moderate), and above 0.5 (strong). Tracks were labeled as original (0), sourced (1), or mixed (excluded for clarity). A chi-squared test showed a significant difference ($p = 0.0378$) in emotional intensity distributions between soundtrack types. Original scores had

a higher proportion of strong emotional responses (64.0%) than sourced soundtracks (58.9%), while sourced tracks elicited more neutral responses (20.2% vs. 11.9%). These findings support the idea that original scores evoke stronger emotional reactions than commercial tracks.

5 Discussion

Minor keys showed no significant effect on valence, challenging the traditional link between minor chords and sadness. This may result from limited sample size and sparse data, which reduced statistical power. The lack of visuals and subjective interpretation might contribute but likely play a secondary role. These findings suggest that the emotional impact of film music is more complex than simple associations between chord quality and emotion. Future studies with larger samples could improve reliability.

Weak correlations between individual musical features and emotional responses imply that single features alone are not sufficient to capture the full emotional experience. This highlights an important implication for MER models: emotion prediction requires composite, higher-level modelling integrating multiple musical dimensions. Higher-level features also showed limited patterns, likely due to individual differences and the inherent ambiguity of film music without visual or narrative context. This ambiguity may itself be an artistic strength, allowing diverse interpretations.

By isolating film music from visuals, this study offers a first step toward multimodal emotion research. While generic MER features provided useful baselines, film-specific traits such as leitmotifs and orchestration remain important directions for future work. The predominance of instrumental excerpts (243/300) and the minority containing lyrics (57/300) further suggests that lyrical content should be carefully considered in future studies.

5.1 Interpretation of Preliminary Experiment Results

The preliminary study highlights the subjective nature of emotional perception in film music. Participants detected emotional changes but found it difficult to verbalize them, indicating challenges in emotional annotation. Variability in responses may arise from music selection and study design, underscoring the personal and nuanced character of emotional reactions. For MER research, this reinforces the need for context-aware, multimodal models. For film composition, it confirms that ambiguity can be a deliberate and effective artistic device.

6 Limitations and Future Work

Future research should examine the interplay of music, visuals, and context, alongside cultural influences on emotion perception. Larger samples and physiological measures (e.g., heart rate) could deepen insights, while focusing on specific subsets might enhance reliability. The preliminary experiment showed no clear differences across professional backgrounds, likely due to small sample

size and limited stimuli. Brief participant responses suggest the need for clearer emotional descriptors.

A multimodal annotation approach, including emotional, visual, and sensory descriptors (e.g., imagery, texture) could provide richer insights. Context is crucial, as narrative, visuals, genre, personal preferences, and film familiarity influence emotional responses, sometimes overriding the music's intent [7]. Expanding the dataset to include works by indie and female composers aims to explore whether unique musical structures or cultural perspectives evoke distinct emotional reactions. This aligns with the broader goal of understanding how diverse musical contexts shape emotion perception.

Future studies should refine emotional annotations, expand data collection, and investigate group-based emotional experiences. Analyzing higher-level and combined musical features, including expressivity, which has shown effectiveness in emotion analysis [21], alongside a more diverse dataset, will enhance the robustness and applicability of findings.

7 Conclusions

This study highlights the complexity of emotional shifts in film music, with arousal responses showing greater consistency in responses than valence. While low-level features, such as ZCR, demonstrated weak correlations with arousal, chord types had a more pronounced effect, particularly on arousal. High-level features like danceability and rhythmic tonal elements showed minimal impact. These findings contribute to the understanding of time-based emotions in film music, and the application of advanced features and techniques could further enhance our comprehension of how film music manipulates emotions, offering valuable insights for both emotional theory and media applications.

References

1. Abel, D.: Sound and Image: Experimental Music and the Popular Horror Film (1960 to the present day). Ph.D. thesis, University of Central Lancashire (2008)
2. Aljanaki, A., Wiering, F., Veltkamp, R., et al.: Computational modeling of induced emotion using gems. In: Proceedings of the 15th Conference of the International Society for Music Information Retrieval (ISMIR 2014). pp. 373–378 (2014)
3. Alluri, V., Toiviainen, P., Jääskeläinen, I.P., Glerean, E., Sams, M., Brattico, E.: Large-scale brain networks emerge from dynamic processing of musical timbre, key and rhythm. *Neuroimage* **59**(4), 3677–3689 (2012)
4. Bogdanov, D., Wack, N., Gómez, E., Gulati, S., Herrera, P., Mayor, O., Roma, G., Salamon, J., Zapata, J.R., Serra, X., et al.: *Essentia*: An audio analysis library for music information retrieval. In: ISMIR. vol. 13, pp. 493–498 (2013)
5. Brotzer, J., Mosqueda, E., Gorro, K.: Predicting emotion in music through audio pattern analysis. In: IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering. vol. 482, p. 012021. IOP Publishing (2019)
6. Crocker, R.O., Fazekas, G.: Temporal analysis of emotion perception in film music: Insights from the fme-24 dataset. In:

- Proceedings of the 21st Sound and Music Computing Conference. pp. 247–252 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14338011>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14338011>
7. Eerola, T.: Are the emotions expressed in music genre-specific? an audio-based evaluation of datasets spanning classical, film, pop and mixed genres. *Journal of New Music Research* **40**(4), 349–366 (2011)
 8. Egermann, H., Fernando, N., Chuen, L., McAdams, S.: Music induces universal emotion-related psychophysiological responses: comparing canadian listeners to congolese pygmies. *Frontiers in psychology* **5**, 1341 (2015)
 9. Elowsson, A., Friberg, A.: Tempo estimation by modelling perceptual speed. *Music Inf. Retrieval Eval. Ex.(MIREX)* (2013)
 10. Freedman, D., Kohler, E., Tutschku, H.: Correlating extracted and ground-truth harmonic data in music retrieval tasks. In: *ISMIR*. pp. 561–567 (2015)
 11. Friberg, A., Schoonderwaldt, E., Hedblad, A., Fabiani, M., Elowsson, A.: Using listener-based perceptual features as intermediate representations in music information retrieval. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* **136**(4), 1951–1963 (2014)
 12. Furstenu, M.: *Film genre: the pragmatics of classification* (1995)
 13. Gong, X., Yuan, R., Qian, H., Chen, Y., Cohn, A.G.: Emotion regulation music recommendation based on feature selection. In: *New Trends in Intelligent Software Methodologies, Tools and Techniques*. vol. 337, pp. 486–495. IOS Press (2021)
 14. Grekow, J.: Audio features dedicated to the detection and tracking of arousal and valence in musical compositions. *Journal of Information and Telecommunication* **2**(3), 322–333 (2018)
 15. Herrera, P., Streich, S.: Detrended fluctuation analysis of music signals: Danceability estimation and further semantic characterization. In: *Audio Engineering Society Convention 118*. Audio Engineering Society (2005)
 16. Hevner, K.: Experimental studies of the elements of expression in music. *The American journal of psychology* **48**(2), 246–268 (1936)
 17. Lartillot, O., Toiviainen, P.: A matlab toolbox for musical feature extraction from audio. In: *International conference on digital audio effects*. vol. 237, p. 244. Bordeaux (2007)
 18. Mauch, M., Dixon, S.: Approximate note transcription for the improved identification of difficult chords. In: *ISMIR*. pp. 135–140 (2010)
 19. McFee, B., Raffel, C., Liang, D., Ellis, D.P., McVicar, M., Battenberg, E., Nieto, O.: librosa: Audio and music signal analysis in python. *SciPy* **2015**, 18–24 (2015)
 20. Morgan, F., Mooney, J.: ‘the same trade as mozart’: Convincing the sceptics of electronic music’s value. *Journal of Popular Television* **9**(1), 55–77 (2021)
 21. Panda, R., Malheiro, R., Paiva, R.P.: Novel audio features for music emotion recognition. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* **11**(4), 614–626 (2018)
 22. Panda, R., Malheiro, R., Paiva, R.P.: Audio features for music emotion recognition: a survey. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* **14**(1), 68–88 (2020)
 23. Peeters, G., et al.: A large set of audio features for sound description (similarity and classification) in the cuidado project. *CUIDADO Ist Project Report* **54**(0), 1–25 (2004)
 24. PS, S., Mahalakshmi, G.: Emotion models: a review. *International Journal of Control Theory and Applications* **10**(8), 651–657 (2017)
 25. Rovenko, E.: Oral session 11 music and perception. In: *3rd International Conference Psychology and Music–Interdisciplinary Encounters: Book of Abstracts*. p. 87
 26. Russell, J.A.: A circumplex model of affect. *Journal of personality and social psychology* **39**(6), 1161 (1980)

27. Schaefer, A., Nils, F., Sanchez, X., Philippot, P.: Assessing the effectiveness of a large database of emotion-eliciting films: A new tool for emotion researchers. *Cognition and emotion* **24**(7), 1153–1172 (2010)
28. Wei, C., Kronland-Martinet, T., Frachi, Y., Barthelet, M.: Influence of music on perceived emotions in film. *AES - Journal of the Audio Engineering Society Audio-Acoustics-Application* pp. 1–14 (2022), <https://hal.science/hal-04114230v2>, hAL Id: hal-04114230, version 2 (02-06-2023), License: Attribution
29. Yang, X., Dong, Y., Li, J.: Review of data features-based music emotion recognition methods. *Multimedia systems* **24**, 365–389 (2018)